

Photoluminescence properties of Ce³⁺-doped and Ce³⁺/Mn^{2+/4+} co-doped Y₃Al₅O₁₂ phosphors obtained by crystallization of yttrium aluminate glass with eutectic composition

K. Haladejová-Mihaldová¹, R. Klement¹, M. Parchovianský², A. Prnová³, J. Valúchová³, D. Galusek³

¹ Department of Functional Materials, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín
(E-mail: robert.klement@tnuni.sk)

² Department of Coating Processes, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín

³ Vitrum Laugaricio – Joint Glass Centre of IIC SAS, TnU AD and FCHPT STU, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín

ABSTRACT

The glass in the system Y₂O₃-Al₂O₃ with eutectic composition (76.86 mol. % (60 wt. %) Al₂O₃ and 23.13 mol. % (40 wt. %) Y₂O₃) was prepared by flame-spraying synthesis in the form of glass microspheres from precursor powder synthesized by sol-gel method. The doping level was kept at 0.25 at. % of Ce³⁺. The prepared glass microspheres with composition Y40A60Ce0.25 were found to be XRD amorphous within detection limit. The DSC analysis revealed the two exothermic effects corresponding to crystallization of the sample Y40A60Ce0.25 at characteristic temperatures; peak 1: T_{x1} = 923 °C (onset), T_{p1} = 936 °C (peak), peak 2: T_{x2} = 989 °C and T_{p2} = 1000 °C, respectively. The origin of the two crystallization peaks (exothermic effect) was examined by high temperature XRD (HT XRD) that revealed the crystallization of YAG phase (Y₃Al₅O₁₂) up to 1200 °C. The crystallization of α-Al₂O₃ phase was observed at temperatures above 1300 °C. The both exothermic effects in DSC trace thus unusually correspond to YAG phase crystallization. The crystallization kinetics of prepared glass was interpreted in terms of nucleation growth Johnson–Mehl–Avrami–Kolmogorov (JMAK) model. The polycrystalline phosphors were prepared from the glass by controlled crystallization at selected temperatures. The photoluminescence properties of glass and polycrystalline phosphors were studied in detail. The emission spectrum of Ce³⁺ doped glass Y40A60Ce0.25 under UV excitation at 345 nm exhibits intensive blue emission; broad emission band in spectral range of 365-500 nm with the emission maximum at 407 nm. As temperature of the heat-treatment increases, the intensity of blue emission decreases, indicating that the Ce³⁺ ion is embedded into YAG crystal host. The PL emission spectra (λ_{exc} = 455 nm) of samples heat-treated at different temperatures show typical broad emission band centred at ~550 nm and PL emission intensity depends strongly on the treatment temperature. The maximum of the emission intensity was achieved for polycrystalline sample treated at 1200°C/3h. The luminescence decay of the prepared glass was well fitted with double-exponential function with lifetimes of 8 ns and 34 ns, respectively. The average lifetime of blue emission was found to be 31 ns. The green-yellow luminescence decay of the crystalline samples with Ce³⁺ ions embedded into YAG crystal host, monitored at 525 nm (under 444 nm excitation), was found to be single-exponential with the lifetime of 61 ns. The temperature dependence of the luminescence intensity of polycrystalline sample was similar as for commercial phosphor, at temperature over 150°C even better thermal behaviour was observed. More than 70% of original PL intensity at RT was achieved at temperature 300°C for sample treated (crystallised) at 1200°C/3h, while commercial phosphor exhibit around 60% of the RT

PL intensity at that temperature.

To increase the intensity of orange/red emission in the phosphors PL spectra, the co-doped $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ phosphors with different Mn^{2+} concentration in glass (from 0.5 up to 4 at. % of Mn^{2+}) were prepared and characterised. The two cases were studied: charge compensated system with the $2\text{Al}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{2+} + \text{Si}^{4+}$ substitution and charge non-compensated system. In case of charge compensated system, based on the spectral overlap of the excitation spectra of Ce^{3+} - doped and Mn^{2+} -doped samples, the excitation wavelength 420 and 455 nm was selected. With increasing Mn^{2+} concentration in the host matrix the orange emission due to Mn^{2+} ions in octahedral coordination environment increases as documented by broader plateau of the overall emission (Fig. 1). On the other hand, the PL intensity of the Ce^{3+} ions decreases quite significantly due to the energy transfer (ET) between Ce^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions. Based on the lifetime data of the Ce^{3+} emission, the efficiency of the energy transfer was estimated to be around 15%. The increasing Mn^{2+} concentration also decreases the luminescence quantum yield. In case of charge non-compensated system, the strong emission in the 625-700 nm was observed, indicating the presence of Mn^{4+} ions in the host matrix. Due to the spectral overlap of the excitation spectra of the Ce^{3+} and Mn^{4+} ions in the NUV and blue spectral region, the studied samples were excited at 342 and 450 nm, respectively. When samples excited by UNV light at 342 nm, the significant increase of the emission in red spectral region was observed. On the other hand, as in the previous case, the emission intensity due to the Ce^{3+} ion rapidly decreases as a result of significant energy transfer from Ce^{3+} to Mn^{4+} ions. At blue light excitation, only small increase of the red emission was observed together with significant reduction of Ce^{3+} emission. Due to the ET between the sensitizer (Ce^{3+}) and activator ($\text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$) ions it is reasonable to avoid co-doping in the studied system and instead to use the blend of the phosphors containing the separate luminescence ions in the same host matrix.

Fig.1: The PL emission spectra of charge-compensated (left) and non-compensated system (right)

Keywords: aluminate glass, YAG, Ce^{3+} - Mn^{2+} doped glass, photoluminescence, lifetime, phosphors, pc-WLED, white light.

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